

Data Driven Approach to Detect Anomalous Human Action Detection in Videos - the Making of Ano-AAD Dataset

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Abstract:

This paper presents an anomaly related video dataset consisting of short anomaly videos divided in classes on the basis of the type of abnormal human behavior by which we can detect abnormal human activities in videos. We collected anomaly videos from numerous sites from the web and we also collected video data from various social media websites like youtube and facebook using web scraping method. Our dataset also include videos from other dataset like UCF-Crime etc. Our dataset which we named as ‘Anomalous Action Detection Dataset’ or ‘Ano-AAD’ consists of two super class -1. Normal videos and 2. anomaly videos. Superclass ‘Anomaly videos’ is divided into 9 subclasses Like arrest ,attack,burglary etc. and every class consists of a number of videos according to the type of activity classified by us during data preparation. This dataset will be used for various purposes in different domains like machine learning,deep learning,crowd anomaly,crime detection, human activity recognition and so on.

Keywords:Machine learning,deep learning,crowd anomaly,crime detection, human activity recognition , video anomaly,Abnormal Human Activity Recognition, computer vision,Artificial Intelligence.

Inception and Objective

The primary objective behind the creation of the Ano-AAD dataset was to address the pressing need for a comprehensive, well-annotated collection of video footage that can be used to train and evaluate models for detecting anomalous human actions. Recognizing the limitations of existing datasets, which often lack diversity and sufficient examples of real-world scenarios, we embarked on a meticulous process to gather, annotate, and validate a diverse array of videos. Our goal was to ensure that the dataset encompasses a wide variety of environments and actions, thereby providing a robust foundation for the development of advanced anomaly detection algorithms.

Data Collection Process

The data collection process for the Ano-AAD dataset was both extensive and methodical. We identified and selected videos from various social media platforms, such as Facebook and YouTube, as well as other online sources. These videos were chosen to represent a broad spectrum of real-world scenarios, including both typical daily activities and less frequent, but critical, anomalous events. Each video was carefully reviewed to ensure it met our criteria for relevance, clarity, and authenticity.

Categorization and Annotation

A cornerstone of the Ano-AAD dataset is its detailed categorization and annotation of human actions. Each video clip was meticulously labeled to differentiate between normal activities—such as walking, sitting, and working—and anomalous behaviors, which include arrests, burglaries, explosions, fighting, fire raising, ill treatment, traffic irregularities, attacks, and other violent acts. This comprehensive annotation process was essential to creating a dataset that accurately reflects the complexities of real-world surveillance challenges. Our team of annotators underwent rigorous training to ensure consistency and reliability in the labeling process, and multiple rounds of validation were conducted to maintain high-quality annotations.

Ethical Considerations

Throughout the data collection and annotation process, we adhered to strict ethical guidelines and privacy regulations. All videos were sourced from publicly available content, and efforts were made to anonymize individuals to protect their privacy. We prioritized compliance with data protection principles, ensuring that our work not only advanced technological capabilities but also respected the rights and privacy of individuals depicted in the footage.

Technical Specifications

The Ano-AAD dataset comprises a total of 395 videos, amounting to 9.24 GB of data and a cumulative duration of 12 hours and 07 minutes. Each video was processed to maintain a uniform format and resolution, typically standardized to

MP4 and 30 FPS frame rate, respectively. This consistency in video quality ensures that the dataset can be seamlessly integrated into various machine learning models and computer vision algorithms, facilitating the development and testing of anomaly detection systems.

Dataset Specification Table:

Subject	Computer science,Artificial Intelligence
Specific subject area	Machine learning,deep learning,crowd anomaly,crime detection, human activity recognition, abnormal human activity recognition using videos.
How we collected data	We collected data using web scraping From numerous websites like youtube and facebook.
Data format	MP4 digital multimedia container format
File extension	.mp4
Data collection parameters	<p>Source Selection: We collected data using web scraping From numerous websites like youtube and facebook.</p> <p>Scenario Diversity: To capture a comprehensive range of human behaviors, we focused on a variety of real-world environments, including public spaces, indoor settings, and other everyday locations where both normal and anomalous activities are likely to occur. This diversity ensures the dataset's applicability to a broad range of surveillance and safety applications.</p>

Video Quality

- Resolution :320x240
- Frame Rate :30

Video Codec: Videos were encoded using H.264 codec

Anomaly Types: 9

Video Length : 12 hours 07 minutes
size :9.24 GB

Ethical Considerations: For ethical considerations, all videos in the dataset were sourced from publicly available content and were anonymized to protect the privacy and identity of individuals depicted

Metadata and Annotation: The dataset includes comprehensive metadata and annotations, providing detailed information such as scenario types, action labels, timestamps, and source origins for each video

Data preprocessing: We perform Data Preprocessing in the dataset mainly to reduce the number of computations and enhance easy training of our deep learning model. The following are done:-

1.Read the video files from the dataset and resize the frames to a fixed width and height.

2.Normalize the data range in [0,1] by dividing 255.

Here frame size is 64*64(height*width)

Sequence length is 20

We define frames_extraction() that will create a list containing the resized and normalized frames of a video whose path is passed as

	<p>argument. The function will read the video frame by frame, but not all frames are added to the list as we will only need an evenly distributed sequence length of frames.</p> <p>The dataset is split into Train(75%) and Test(25%) [for experiment purpose]</p>
<p>Description of data collection</p>	<p>The data collection process for the Ano-AAD dataset was both extensive and methodical. We identified and selected videos from various social media platforms, such as Facebook and YouTube, as well as other online sources. These videos were chosen to represent a broad spectrum of real-world scenarios, including both typical daily activities and less frequent, but critical, anomalous events. Each video was carefully reviewed to ensure it met our criteria for relevance, clarity, and authenticity.</p>
<p>Data accessibility</p>	<p>The dataset is made publicly available for future research to download from kaggle in zip format. Metadata is made available to download as json format.</p> <p>Dataset download link : https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/sayantnroy/10121999/anomalous-action-detection-dataset Researchers are required to comply with the terms of the license CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 when using the dataset. Detailed documentation, including our work link will be provided at the</p>

	end of the paper, For inquiries or further assistance, please contact us.
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Value of Our Dataset

- The data can be used for computer vision and machine learning and deep learning to improve Human Activity recognition, Abnormal Human Activity classification ,crowd anomaly and crime detection.
- Collection of such data demands skillful resources and specialist equipment, therefore making it costly to collect.
- It can be used to research, develop, and improve robotic and/or intelligent systems

Description of Our Dataset

Abnormal human activity recognition[1] is the most researched topic in the areas of machine learning and deep learning nowadays. Researchers have used a large number of methods [2-9] like analyzing abnormal activities [2] applying multiple machine learning[11]and deep learning methodology such as CNN[4][6],RNN,LSTM[3],GAN on various datasets[9][10].

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Experimental Design, Materials, and Methods for Ano-AAD Dataset

Objective

We aimed to create the Ano-AAD dataset to detect anomalous human actions in videos. This dataset, gathered from various social media platforms and websites such as Facebook and YouTube, encompasses a variety of normal and anomalous activities.

Experimental Design

1. **Scenario Selection:** We identified and selected diverse real-world scenarios from social media and websites where anomalous actions are likely to be captured.
2. **Action Categories:** We defined a list of normal and anomalous actions for each scenario, including arrests, burglaries, explosions, and more.
3. **Data Collection Strategy:** We utilized videos from social media platforms and websites, ensuring ethical considerations and privacy compliance during data collection.

Materials

1. **Video Sources:** We sourced videos from social media platforms such as Facebook and YouTube.
2. **Annotation Tools:** We employed video annotation software ,custom-built tools to facilitate precise action labeling.
3. **Storage and Processing Hardware:** We utilized high-capacity storage solutions and powerful computing hardware for video processing and annotation tasks.

Methods

1. **Data Collection:**
 - **Sources:** We collected videos from various social media platforms and websites, ensuring a diverse range of scenarios and actions.
 - **Selection Criteria:** We chose videos that depicted clear instances of normal and anomalous actions, ensuring video quality was sufficient for analysis and annotation.
2. **Preprocessing:**
 - We converted all videos to a standard format (e.g., MP4) and 30 fps speed for consistency.
 - We segmented videos into clips containing single actions to simplify annotation and training.
3. **Annotation:**
 - We trained annotators on the protocol and conducted inter-annotator agreement tests to ensure reliability.
 - We annotated each clip with action labels (normal or anomalous) and temporal boundaries using the chosen annotation tool.
 - We reviewed and validated annotations through multiple rounds to maintain high quality.
4. **Dataset Compilation:**
 - We organized annotated clips into a structured format, including metadata such as scenario type, action labels, and timestamps.
 - We split the dataset into training, validation, and test sets, ensuring a balanced representation of normal and anomalous actions across all splits.
5. **Quality Assurance:**
 - We performed statistical analysis to verify the distribution of actions and ensure dataset diversity.
 - We conducted pilot tests with baseline models to identify and address any potential biases or issues in the dataset.

Folder Hierarchy of Anomalous Action Detection (Ano-AAD) dataset

Dataset Statistics

Tool :Our dataset statistics are collected using the **mediainfo** command line tool which is available in ubuntu 22.04.

Machine: We used ASUS Celeron Dual Core - (4 GB RAM/1 TB HDD) X543MA-GQ1015T Laptop to evaluate our dataset statistics.

Statistics Terminology:

1.dataset size is given in MB and GB. MB stands for megabytes and GB Stands for gigabytes.

2.video duration of our dataset is given in HH:MM format(Hours and Minutes format)

Table 2: Ano-AAD Dataset Superclass statistics

Serial Number	Dataset Superclass	Total number Of videos	size	duration(HH:MM)
1.	Normal videos	41	527.9 MB	0:41
2.	Anomaly videos	354	8.7GB	11:25
	total	395	9.2GB	12 :07

Table 3: Subclasses in anomaly videos and related statistics

Serial Number	Anomaly Class	Total Number of videos	size	duration(HH:MM)
1.	Arrest	49	1.7GB	2:10
2.	Burglary	48	948.7MB	1:26
3.	Explosion	49	773MB	1:01
4.	Fighting	50	2.0GB	2:23
5.	Fire Raising	49	999.4MB	1:20
6.	ill treatment	32	812.5MB	1:07
7.	traffic irregularities	13	79.3MB	0:05
8.	Attack	38	543.8MB	0:41
9.	violence	26	836MB	1:08
	Total	354	8.7GB	11:25

Table 4: Average duration calculation

Total video duration average	110.43038sec
Superclass Normal videos average duration	60sec
Superclass abnormal videos average duration	116.101695sec

Future Scope

This work's data was collected from various datasets, websites, Social media channels like . youtube ,twitter,facebook. The authors subsequently used various python packages like beautiful soup for pulling data from the website and used their own pre-processing technique. The dataset has 9 types of criminal actions like abuse ,arson etc. The authors have made this dataset for Machine Learning, Deep Learning related works. which can be further extended to surveillance, automation and sensor related crime detection works.

Ethics Statement

Ethical considerations were rigorously observed throughout the creation of this dataset, which consists of anonymized videos sourced from publicly available content on social media platforms and websites. Prior to inclusion, efforts were made to ensure the protection of individuals' privacy and confidentiality. The dataset does not include personally identifiable information, and all videos were obtained and used in accordance with the terms and conditions set forth by the respective platforms. Researchers are encouraged to uphold ethical guidelines and consider potential implications when using this dataset for further analysis or application

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors state that they have no known conflicting financial interests or personal relationships that may have influenced the work presented in this publication.

Credit Author Statement

Avisek Mondal :,Data collection, Dataset Creator,Software, Writing – draft;
Sayantan Roy: Resources, Writing – original , draft and Dataset Statistics;
Sombit Bose : Methodology, Resources,Concept ,Software;
Dr. Partha Ghosh: Concept, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank our Project Guide Dr. Partha Ghosh for his valuable advice .

Important Links

1. <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/sayantanroy10121999/anomalous-action-detection-dataset/data>
2. <https://journals.bohrpub.com/index.php/bijscit/article/view/302/4605>
3. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28735.52644>
4. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28211.23845>
5. <http://dx.doi.org/10.54646/bijscit.2023.29>
6. <http://dx.doi.org/10.34740/kaggle/dsv/8717699>
7. <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/11wIzL7uXvfXrKXQfURQ0MWfX3sea8kzF4CYltbtchjU/edit?usp=sharing>

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